

Civil Servant Neutrality in Regent Elections (A Review of Communication in Bawaslu Supervision in Gowa Regency)

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Abstract:

This study aims to analyse the non-neutrality of civil servants in the 2024 regional head elections in Gowa Regency; communication in the supervision of the Gowa Regency Election Supervisory Agency (Bawaslu) to realise civil servant neutrality; and the actions of the Gowa Regency Bawaslu in handling violations of civil servant neutrality. The research method used was qualitative field research. The research approach used was organisational communication theory. The data sources were primary and secondary data. The data collection methods consisted of observation, interviews, and documentation. The results of the study show that the factors causing civil servants to be non-neutral in the 2024 regional head elections in Gowa Regency are pressure from the incumbent or candidates who support the incumbent; temptation, personal interests in positions or benefits; kinship or connections; and supervision that is not yet comprehensive and a lack of supervisory human resources. Bawaslu conducted communication in the form of socialisation, public education, participatory supervision through dialogue and seminars, coordination with local governments, BKD, and inspectorates, as well as media campaigns. In handling violations, Bawaslu issued appeal letters, processed reports, and enforced the law through coordination with the Integrated Law Enforcement Centre (Gakkumdu), the State Civil Service Agency (BKN), and related agencies. Overall, this study emphasises the importance of educational, coordinative, and participatory institutional communication, as well as the need to strengthen regulations and guidance for ASN to maintain bureaucratic neutrality. These efforts are strategic steps toward building a professional, independent, and integrity-driven bureaucracy in the implementation of regional elections.

Keywords: Neutrality, ASN, Supervision.

INTRODUCTION

Direct regional head elections (Pilkada) have opened the door to democracy in Indonesia. Since the implementation of Law No. 22 of 1999 on Regional Government, there has been a shift in procedure. The opening of channels for the community to

directly elect their regional heads has given rise to the figure of a leader with their own strengths. This format has resulted in the practice of political education and leadership at the same time. Local sons are considered to have specific knowledge of the region, including its potential.

This assumption expresses that local sons are worthy and capable of managing the needs of their region's resources. Over time, independent regional head candidates have contributed to democracy, which previously depended on the existence of political parties. This policy is not wrong, considering that the recruitment channel for candidates in previous regional elections was only projected by political parties. (Muttaqin et al., 2021)

Civil servants are faced with a dilemma between neutrality and loyalty to their superiors. The involvement of civil servants in politics occurs because they hold strategic positions within the government. Many civil servants are found to be involved in practical politics, thereby violating the principle of civil servant neutrality. The non-neutrality of civil servants has an impact or consequence that may benefit one party. (Saputra, 2020)

The bureaucracy, as the daily implementer of government, must maintain its neutrality in elections, because if there is politicisation among the bureaucracy, such as mutual support for specific candidates, it will disrupt the democratic process and potentially lead to abuse of power for political interests. If this happens, it will be challenging to achieve elections based on the principles of honesty and fairness, in addition to neglecting public services, which will have an impact on the stability of the nation and State. (Pradono, 2019)

Direct regional elections by the people are a manifestation of the restoration of the fundamental rights of the people to elect leaders in the regions. The people have the opportunity and sovereignty to determine regional leaders directly, freely, and confidentially without intervention. However, the implementation of regional elections does not always run ideally. ASN, as civil servants who are obliged to provide public services, are often co-opted by political interests. Politicians and regional head candidates who are not statesmen frequently take advantage of the bureaucracy for their political interests. (Sutrisno, 2019)

The existence of ASN in Indonesia is considered increasingly important for the administration of government and development; the smooth running of the government and development is inseparable from the participation of the State Civil Apparatus. Therefore, the government has made serious efforts to formulate this into a legal framework that is becoming increasingly perfect. Since Indonesia's independence, there have been several laws regulating all aspects of civil servants. (Ericson, 2022)

So far, ASN has been a subject of debate in Indonesia's democratic life. Government Regulation No. 5 of 1999 Jo. Government Regulation No. 12 of 1999 and finally Government Regulation No. 37 of 2004 concerning the Prohibition of Civil Servants from Becoming Members of Political Parties are intended to address the issues that have been occurring. The regulation is designed to ensure that civil servants remain neutral in political parties. This regulation is also expected to bring a breath of fresh air to political party life in Indonesia, as civil servants have been used to support only one political party. With this regulation, it is hoped that political life in Indonesia will be more democratic and free from mutual suspicion. (Abdullah, 2018)

Regarding violations of ASN neutrality in regional elections, there are two interesting phenomena. First, the spread of patronage among regional administrators and their subordinate structural officials: patronage, which is the unlimited authority of regional administrators to build relationships with their subordinates as clients. Meanwhile, one of the characteristics of client culture is the tendency of ASN to submit and obey their patrons, namely, regional administrators. In this case, ethnic similarities and regional relationships become the basis for cohesion. Patron-client networks in regional elections contribute significantly to increasing violations of ASN neutrality in regional head elections. (Suswanta & Setiawan, 2023)

Second, the dilemma faced by ASN due to existing regulations. As public officials, ASN must be neutral and impartial. However, on the other hand, ASN must also take a political stance or side, especially if the defense returns to function. This dilemma stems from Government Regulation No. 11 of 2017 concerning Civil Servant Management, which states that the Regional Head (under the authority of the President) is the Civil Service Supervisory Official (PPK) who has the authority to appoint, transfer, and dismiss ASN. Conversely, based on Article 71 paragraph (2) of the Regional Election Law No. 10 of 2016, regional heads are prohibited from replacing officials within six months before the date of the candidate pair's appointment until the end of their term of office (unless they obtain written permission from the Minister). In fact, many violations occur in strategic areas and are not accompanied by sanctions.

Several civil service regulations explicitly provide "legal loopholes" that drag civil servants into the political vortex. Article 53 of Civil Service Law No. 5 of 2014 appoints provincial governors and regents/mayors as regional civil service supervisory officials, for whom the President gives the authority to decide on the appointment, transfer, and dismissal of middle-level and operational officials. In addition, Article 54 explains that provincial and regency/city secretaries, as officials who are given authority, only have authority related to performance-based ASN management and must still consult with the governor and regional civil service supervisory officials (regents/mayors). This provision is open to multiple interpretations or is ambiguous. This regulatory ambiguity is the primary source of violations of ASN neutrality. (Suswanta & Setiawan, 2023)

The researchers chose the Gowa Regency Bawaslu as the location for their research because the regional head elections in Gowa Regency are one of the areas in South Sulawesi that have pretty high local political dynamics. Civil servant neutrality was chosen as the focus of this research because civil servants are a crucial aspect of maintaining the quality and integrity of democracy at the local level. However, there are still civil servants who are easily influenced by practical politics, so civil servant neutrality needs to be questioned.

Regarding the non-neutrality of ASN in regional elections that took place in several regencies/cities, including in Gowa Regency, there were cases handled by Bawaslu Gowa Regency during the regional elections. Based on these findings, the ASN involved used various methods, some posting on social media and others openly campaigning for one of the candidates.

Some of these findings have been forwarded to the relevant institutions for follow-up, as the institutions are authorized to handle cases of civil servants violating the principle of neutrality. Violations of the neutrality rule by civil servants can even lead to criminal charges.

In Islam, civil servants are known as "Diwan" or State administrators who are responsible for recording government property, such as territories under State control and State assets, as well as the people responsible for them, such as soldiers and employees.

Diwan or administration in Islam is divided into four parts, namely: *diwan* (administration) which records the appointment of soldiers and the determination of their salaries; *diwan* (administration) which records data on State territories along with the levies that must be collected and the rights that must be granted; *diwan* (administration) which records the appointment and dismissal of civil servants; *the diwan* (administration) that records the income and expenditure of *Baitul Mal* (the State treasury). (Al-Mawardi, 2000)

Every time an election period approaches, the neutrality of civil servants will be tested and become a momentum to reaffirm the bureaucratic reforms that have been ongoing. The spirit of bureaucratic reform can be seen in the collective awareness of civil servants about the importance of being professional and not getting involved in practical politics ahead of regional elections, where ASN are highly vulnerable to involvement in practical politics, as some ASN have emotional ties to incumbent regional leaders. Therefore, this study will examine the extent of the role of the Gowa Regency Bawaslu in communicating with ASN to maintain neutrality ahead of regional elections.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Neutrality of Civil Servants (ASN)

The neutrality of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) is defined as a principle that requires ASN to be impartial from any influence, not to take sides in practical political interests, and to serve the community professionally and fairly. This definition can be seen from various perspectives, including law, ethics, and public service.

From a legal perspective, the neutrality of ASN is regulated in legislation to ensure that the bureaucracy does not become a political tool.

- a. Law Number 5 of 2014 concerning ASN: Article 2 explicitly states that one of the principles in the implementation of ASN policy and management is neutrality.
- b. Law Number 20 of 2023 concerning ASN: Reinforces this mandate by prohibiting ASN from becoming members or administrators of political parties.
- c. Government Regulation Number 94 of 2021 concerning Civil Servant Discipline: Regulates explicit provisions and sanctions for ASN who violate the principle of neutrality in general elections.

Furthermore, from an ethical perspective, civil service neutrality is related to the values of professionalism and integrity. Several aspects are explained, namely:

- a. Code of ethics: ASN must refrain from conflicts of interest involving themselves, groups, or certain factions.
- b. Freedom from influence: The ethics of neutrality require civil servants not to be influenced by any group and to remain independent in carrying out their duties.
- c. Moral integrity: Avoid actions that undermine public trust, such as siding with specific candidates, which can lead to abuse of authority and conflicts of interest.

Furthermore, from a public service perspective, ASN neutrality ensures that the services provided to the community are non-discriminatory and of high quality. The explanation is as follows:

- a. Fair service: Neutrality ensures that ASN serves the public without discrimination based on political preferences. Services must be provided with respect, courtesy, and equality to all members of the community.
- b. Objectivity and professionalism: ASN must focus on their duties as professional and high-quality public servants, free from political pressure.
- c. Public trust: Neutrality is an important pillar that maintains public confidence in the government. When the public believes that ASN serves them reasonably, the legitimacy of the government will increase.

2. Organizational Communication

Organizational communication is an essential field in communication studies because it examines how messages, information, and meaning are managed in an organizational context. Eisenberg, Goodall, and Trethewey emphasize that managerial communication is not merely a process of conveying messages from superiors to subordinates, but also involves a process of negotiating meaning among members of the organization. They introduce the concept of *strategic ambiguity*, which is the use of messages that are deliberately made ambiguous to accommodate various interests within the organization. Thus, organizational communication serves not only to convey instructions but also to maintain cohesion, build consensus, and reduce conflict. (Eric M. Eisenberg, H. L. Goodall, Jr., 2010)

Meanwhile, Miller views organizational communication from a more systematic perspective by dividing organizational communication theories into several approaches, such as classical, *human relations*, systems, and organizational culture. According to him, organizational communication is "*the creation and exchange of messages within a network of interdependent relationships to cope with environmental uncertainty.*" This definition emphasizes that organizational communication is part of the process of organizational adaptation to its environment. This means that communication does not only take place vertically, but also horizontally and across units so that organizations can deal with external dynamics, such as policy changes, competition, and political pressure. (Miller & Barbour, 2014)

Putnam and Nicotera then strengthened organizational communication studies by developing *the constitutive perspective*. They emphasized that organizations themselves are formed and maintained through communication practices. In other words, organizations are not merely containers for communication activities, but rather exist because of communication. This perspective is known as *Communication Constitutes Organization* (CCO). Within this framework, every interaction, meeting, rule, and symbol is viewed as a communication process that collectively shapes the reality of the organization. (Putnam & Anne M. Nicotera, 2009)

3. Bureaucracy Theory

Weber's concept of ideal bureaucracy emphasizes professionalism and rationality in running the bureaucratic machine. To appreciate his efforts in creating this concept, we need to understand the logic of Weber's approach and the innovative ideas he put forward that were relevant to the context of his time. His ideal bureaucracy is an abstract description that helps us understand the structure of social life.(Iriawan & Edyanto, 2024)

Weber argued that this ideal concept helps compare bureaucracies between various organizations in the world. By separating the reality that occurs from the perfect idea of an organization, we can conclude why these differences arise and what factors distinguish them. Furthermore, Weber wanted to explain that the ideal concept illustrates that every bureaucracy or government administration has a definite structure in which all functions are carried out rationally.

There are seven ideal criteria for bureaucracy described by Weber, including the following.

- a. A clear division of labor.
- b. A clear hierarchy of authority.
- c. A high degree of formalization.
- d. Impersonal nature.
- e. Decision-making regarding employee placement based on ability.
- f. Career paths for employees.
- g. Organizational life is clearly separated from personal life. (Iriawan & Edyanto, 2024)

4. The Concept of Neutrality in Indonesia

In 2024, elections (Pemilu) in Indonesia will be held simultaneously, with legislative elections and presidential elections taking place alongside regional head elections in various regions. The neutrality of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) is a significant concern in this context, given the vital role of *State apparatuses* in ensuring that the democratization process is fair and transparent. (Montheza et al., 2024)

In fact, several interesting phenomena often occur during the implementation of elections, namely that some State officials, including the president and ministers, who are supposed to have neutral political positions, are seen to openly show their political preferences through symbols and actions in the public sphere. This contrasts with the stringent limitations imposed on civil servants, who are also required to remain neutral during election periods. Civil servants are even strictly prohibited from displaying numerical symbols or other political symbols in hand gestures when photographed, as stipulated in Government Regulation (PP) No. 94 of 2021 concerning Civil Servant Discipline.

The rules aimed at maintaining the neutrality of ASN were also introduced as an effort to ensure the integrity and independence of ASN in carrying out their duties during the political process (Adnan, 2023). One of these regulations is the Joint Decree (SKB) on Guidelines for the Development and Supervision of the Neutrality of State Civil Apparatus (ASN) Employees in the Implementation of Elections and Selections, issued by the Government. Various relevant agencies, including the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform, the Minister of Home Affairs, the Acting Head

of the State Civil Service Agency, the Chair of the Civil Service Commission, and the Chair of the Election Supervisory Agency, signed this SKB.

Violations of these rules can result in severe sanctions for ASN, ranging from warnings to criminal sanctions, including performance allowance deductions, demotions, dismissal from office, and even termination as a civil servant/ASN. This phenomenon creates a significant difference in treatment between political officials and ASN in terms of political involvement. As mentioned earlier, political involvement can no longer be proven by attending the campaign of one of the candidates; even a hand gesture can indicate that someone supports a particular candidate. Finger poses or emphasizing specific numbers and figures, which are then uploaded to social media, will receive various responses and even various sanctions if they are indicated to support a particular candidate. (Montheza et al., 2024)

In the comparative study between academic debates on neutrality versus loyalty, Max Weber's classical bureaucracy theory can be used to analyze the neutrality of civil servants in local elections. Rationality, clear hierarchy, formal rules, and a merit system in recruitment are the foundations of an ideal bureaucracy, according to Weber (1978). The concept of legal-rational authority refers to a situation in which public officials are expected to act based on laws and rules rather than political interests or personal loyalties. Weber's theory is highly relevant in the context of elections because he emphasizes the importance of civil servant neutrality to avoid getting caught up in political patronage practices that can undermine bureaucratic professionalism.

Woodrow Wilson's view of the dichotomy between politics and administration also played an important role. According to Wilson (1887), "administration is outside the proper sphere of politics." From this perspective, civil servants must remain neutral in political contests, as their responsibility is to implement policy, not to determine who is in power. However, there is criticism of this doctrine because the distinction between politics and administration is often unclear in the real world, especially at the local level, where bureaucratic intervention by the political elite is powerful.

Furthermore, academic debate focuses on the neutrality versus loyalty of the bureaucracy. This dilemma is referred to as "the tension between neutrality and responsiveness" by Denhardt and Denhardt (2015). This term refers to the contrast between loyalty to political leaders and the neutral professionalism of the bureaucracy. Bureaucratic loyalty to the ruling government is considered necessary for policy continuity, according to Peters (2010). However, the neutrality of civil servants can be compromised if this loyalty becomes too strong. This can lead to political bias in the bureaucracy.

METHOD

This study uses a *qualitative field research* method. This type of research is used to study natural conditions (as opposed to experiments) where the researcher is the key instrument. (Sugiyono, 2013)

Location: This research was conducted in Gowa Regency, South Sulawesi, specifically in the working area of the Gowa Regency Election Supervisory Agency (Bawaslu) on Jl. Andi Malombassang Sungguminasa, Somba Opu District, Gowa Regency. The research period was one month, from June to July 2025. In conducting the research, the organizational communication theory approach was used. This approach was intended for the dynamic interaction process between organizational units, both formally and

informally, regarding the regulation of rights, obligations, duties, authorities, roles, functions, and distribution of power of units that are interconnected and cooperate to achieve common goals. (Harahap et al., 2022)

This research is a field study categorized as empirical research, so the data sources used are primary, secondary, and tertiary data sources. Then, in determining the informants, the researcher used *purposive sampling*. (Muhaimin, 2020) The informants selected by the researcher for interviews were as follows: Head of the Gowa Regency Election Supervisory Agency (Bawaslu); civil servants; NGO leaders; and community leaders.

Data collection methods included observation, interviews, and documentation. (Yusuf, 2017) . This study used the Miles and Huberman data analysis model, namely: Data Reduction, Data Presentation, and Conclusion Drawing. (Yusuf, 2017)

The selection of informants in this study was based on *purposive sampling*, which is a technique of deliberately determining informants by considering their competence, experience, and relevance to the research problem. The head of the Gowa Regency Bawaslu was chosen because he has the authority, knowledge, and direct experience in supervising the neutrality of ASNs in the implementation of regional elections. The presence of the Bawaslu leader as a key informant enabled the researcher to obtain in-depth data on the strategies, obstacles, and communication practices of supervision carried out by the institution.

In addition, civil servants were also selected as informants because they are the main subjects of the issue of neutrality in regional elections. The views and experiences of civil servants can provide a realistic picture of the extent to which the principle of neutrality is implemented, as well as how political pressure and bureaucratic loyalty influence their attitudes. Furthermore, NGO leaders were considered essential to interview because they have a social control function and are often critical partners in monitoring the democratic process. The perspective of NGOs will enrich the analysis of bureaucratic independence and the effectiveness of Bawaslu's oversight.

Community leaders were also selected as informants because they represent the public voice in assessing the neutrality of civil servants. Public perceptions of civil servant involvement in practical politics greatly influence the legitimacy of the regional election process. By involving community leaders, researchers can obtain an overview of how Bawaslu's oversight communications are received, understood, and responded to by the wider community. Thus, the selection of these four categories of informants through purposive sampling is considered appropriate for producing relevant, in-depth, and comprehensive data in answering the research focus.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The neutrality of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) in the implementation of regional elections (Pilkada) is a fundamental concept that emphasizes the importance of a professional, objective bureaucracy that is free from political intervention. This principle is not only an ethical norm but also a legal obligation as stipulated in Law Number 5 of 2014 concerning the Civil Service, Law Number 7 of 2017 concerning Elections, and Government Regulation Number 94 of 2021 concerning Civil Servant Discipline. The neutrality of ASN is intended to ensure that the bureaucracy continues to function as a fair and impartial public servant, so that the democratic process can take place honestly, transparently, and with integrity.

In the context of the Gowa Regency, data shows that civil service neutrality still faces significant challenges. Based on records from the Gowa Regency Central Statistics Agency (BPS), as of December 2023, there were 6,323 ASN, consisting of 2,218 men and 4,105 women. Meanwhile, throughout 2024, the Gowa Regency Election Supervisory Agency (Bawaslu) received 14 reports related to alleged violations of ASN neutrality. The forms of violations found varied, ranging from involvement in practical politics, politically charged activities on social media, to the misuse of State facilities to support specific candidates. This fact shows a gap between the idealism of the law and the reality of practice in the field.

The phenomenon of civil servant non-neutrality can be analyzed from various contributing factors. Political pressure from incumbents often influences civil servants to take sides to maintain their positions or career security. In addition, the lure of promotion, personal interests, and kinship ties with candidates are also reasons for civil servants to engage in practical politics. The strong culture of patronage in the bureaucracy means that loyalty to political figures is prioritized over professionalism. On the other hand, the limitations of the supervision carried out by Bawaslu, both due to a lack of human resources and the limited scope of supervision, also provide room for violations to occur.

The implications of violating civil servant neutrality are severe, both for individual civil servants, bureaucratic institutions, and the democratic system itself. Civil servants who violate the rules can be subject to administrative and even criminal sanctions, while institutionally, such actions tarnish the image of a government that should uphold professionalism. Furthermore, violations of neutrality can undermine public trust in the conduct of elections, as they create the perception that the bureaucracy is no longer objective and is biased toward specific political interests. Therefore, stricter supervision, firm enforcement of sanctions, and the strengthening of a culture of integrity among civil servants are necessary to ensure that the principle of neutrality is truly realized.

In this context, the Gowa Regency Bawaslu has a strategic role to ensure that the neutrality of ASN is maintained. Efforts to disseminate information on regulations, political education, and community involvement in supervision are essential preventive measures. On the other hand, the courage of ASN to reject political intervention and uphold professionalism must continue to be strengthened through a fair meritocracy system that is free from patronage pressure. Thus, ASN neutrality can truly become the foundation for the realization of honest, fair, and integrity-based regional elections in Gowa Regency.

CONCLUSION

The neutrality of civil servants in regional elections is a crucial aspect in upholding the principles of democracy and bureaucratic professionalism. In Gowa Regency, although the law has emphasized the obligation of ASN not to be involved in practical politics, the reality on the ground shows that there are still violations triggered by political pressure, loyalty to specific figures, and weak supervision. The non-neutrality of ASN not only violates the law but also has the potential to damage the integrity of the bureaucracy and reduce public trust in the democratic process. Therefore, strengthening supervision by Bawaslu, imposing strict sanctions, and internalizing the values of professionalism and integrity among ASN are urgent steps that must be taken. Thus, ASN neutrality will not only become a legal norm but also a strong bureaucratic culture that supports the implementation of honest, fair, and integrity-based regional elections.

REFERENCES

- Abdullah, L. O. D. (2018). Criminal Sanctions for Civil Servants (PNS) who are Not Neutral in the Regional Head Elections (PILKADA) of Baubau City Based on the State Civil Apparatus Law. *Volkgeist Law Journal: National Legal Education Forum*, 2(2), 161.
- Al-Mawardi, I. (2000). Al-Ahkam ash-Shulthaniyyah wal-Wilaayaatud-Diniyyah. In *Trans. Abdul Hayyie al-Kattani and Kamaluddin Nurdin, Constitutional Law and Leadership in Islamic Measurements*.
- Eric M. Eisenberg, H. L. Goodall, Jr., A. T. (2010). *Organizational Communication: Balancing Creativity and Constraint*. Bedford/St. Martin's.
- Ericson, R. J. (2022). Administrative Sanctions against Civil Servants in Regional Head Election Campaign Activities. *Jurnal Hukum Postitum*, 7(1), 176.
- Harahap, S. M., Rizki, J. W. S., & Siregar, E. Z. (2022). *Organizational Communication Strategies*. Prenada Media Group.
- Iriawan, H., & Edyanto. (2024). *Indonesian Bureaucracy*.
- Miller, K., & Barbour, J. (2014). *Organizational Communication: Approaches and Processes*. Cengage Learning.
- Montheza, R., Aminuddin, A. T., & Nugraha, T. (2024). Neutrality of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) in the 2024 Election: A Case Study of Instagram @abdimuda_id. *Electoral Governance Journal of Indonesian Election Governance*, 5 (2), 247–266. <https://doi.org/10.46874/tkp.v5i2.1248>
- Muhaimin. (2020). *Legal Research Methods*. Mataram University Press.
- Muttaqin, M. Z., Ilham, & Idris, U. (2021). Challenges in Implementing Civil Servant Neutrality: A Study of Symbolic Violence in Regional Elections. *Journal of Political Discourse*, 6(1), 1.
- Pradono, N. S. (2019). Civil Servants in the 2019 Elections: Can They Be Neutral? *Journal of Policy Analysis*, 3(1), 53.
- Putnam, L. L., & Anne M. Nicotera. (2009). *Building Theories of Organization: The*

Constitutive Role of Communication. Routledge.

Saputra, A. D. (2020). Prevention and Enforcement of Violations of Civil Servant Neutrality by the Palopo City Election Supervisory Agency in the 2019 Elections. *I La Galigo Journal: Public Administration Journal*, 3(2), 78.

Sugiyono. (2013). *Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D Research Methods* (19th ed.). Alfabeta Publishers.

Suswanta, & Setiawan, A. (2023). Regulatory Ambiguity And Its Implications For The Neutrality Of The State Civil Apparatus In The Vortex Of Practical Politics. *CosmoGov: Journal of Government Science*, 9(2), 112–122.

Sutrisno. (2019). The Principle of Neutrality of the State Civil Apparatus in Regional Head Elections. *IUS QUIA IUSTUM Law Journal*, 26(3), 526.

Yusuf, A. M. (2017). *Research Methods: Quantitative, Qualitative, and Mixed Methods* (1st Edition). Kencana.